

Competency-Based Performance Level for Full Intervention Grade 1 Pupils: Basis for Development of a Contextualized Learning Materials

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the competency-based performance level of full intervention Grade 1 pupils in literacy and numeracy as a basis for the development of contextualized learning materials in selected public elementary schools in Bulan, Sorsogon, during the school year 2023–2024. Specifically, the study identified the least-mastered competencies of pupils and developed validated contextualized intervention materials responsive to their learning needs. The study employed a descriptive-developmental research design utilizing a pre-test approach and the 4D model consisting of Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate. The respondents included 230 full intervention Grade 1 pupils and four master teachers who served as validators of the developed materials. Data were analyzed using frequency count, percentage, and weighted mean. Findings revealed that the least-mastered competencies in numeracy were learning place value, learning addition and subtraction, and counting forward and backward. In literacy, the least-mastered competencies were attaining reading comprehension, determining the first and last sound, and learning phoneme analysis. Based on these findings, contextualized literacy and numeracy learning materials were developed to address the identified competency gaps among the pupils. Validation results showed that the developed materials were rated as very evident in terms of mechanics, content, format, organization, and accuracy. The study concluded that competency-based and contextualized learning materials are essential for addressing the foundational learning needs of full intervention Grade 1 pupils.

KEYWORDS:

literacy, numeracy, remediation, validation, intervention, assessment

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Global and National Learning Recovery Initiatives in Basic Education

Education plays an important role in developing foundational literacy and numeracy competencies necessary for lifelong learning and academic success. However, the COVID-19 pandemic caused severe educational disruptions worldwide, resulting in significant learning loss among early-grade learners. Studies by Wisenöcker et al. (2025), Patrinos, Vegas, and Carter-Rau (2022), and Rosales (2025) revealed that prolonged school closures negatively affected learners' reading and mathematics performance, particularly among primary pupils who relied heavily on structured classroom instruction.

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In response, educational systems worldwide implemented learning recovery initiatives focused on competency-based instruction, remediation, and continuous assessment. UNESCO and UNICEF emphasized the importance of targeted interventions in restoring foundational learning. In the Philippines, EDCOM II Communications (2024)⁴ highlighted the continuing literacy and numeracy crisis among Filipino learners, prompting the Department of Education to strengthen intervention and recovery programs for early-grade pupils.

Several studies also emphasized the effectiveness of contextualized and competency-based instructional materials in improving learner performance. Solis and Pasia (2024), Aceo (2025), and Francisco (2025) found that contextualized interventions and remedial instruction significantly improved learners' literacy, numeracy, and academic engagement among struggling elementary learners.

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1.2 Implementation of 8-Week Learning Recovery Curriculum in Literacy and Numeracy

The Department of Education Region V implemented the 8-Week Learning Recovery Curriculum (LRC) to address learning gaps in literacy and numeracy among Grades 1 to 3 learners in the Bicol Region. The curriculum focused on competency-based remediation, continuous assessment, and differentiated instruction to strengthen foundational learning competencies.

Several studies conducted in the Bicol Region documented the effectiveness of the program. Nobora (2024) found that the implementation of the 8-Week Learning Recovery Curriculum significantly improved the literacy and numeracy performance of Grade 3 learners in selected public elementary schools. Similarly, Miña and Caballes (2023) revealed significant improvement in numeracy competencies among Grade 3 learners in Legazpi City after the implementation of the intervention program.

In Sorsogon City, Domanico and Embile (2025) reported that the curriculum effectively improved the numeracy skills of Grade 1 learners through differentiated activities and continuous assessment. Dianela et al. (2023)¹¹ likewise found that the program significantly enhanced learners' reading competencies in English, Filipino, and Mother Tongue. These findings support the effectiveness of structured intervention programs in improving foundational literacy and numeracy competencies among early-grade learners.

1.3 Challenges, Issues, and Enhancement Strategies in Learning Recovery Program Implementation

Despite the positive effects of intervention programs, several challenges continue to affect the implementation of learning recovery initiatives. Cayabas Jr. and Sumeg-ang (2023) identified limited instructional materials, insufficient resources, and lack of time as major concerns among teachers developing intervention materials. Similarly, Busari, Efeturi, and Sulaimon (2025) emphasized that teacher preparedness and instructional strategies greatly influence the effectiveness of literacy and numeracy interventions.

Parental involvement, learner attendance, and differentiated instruction also affect intervention outcomes. Akkus and Cinkir (2022) emphasized that absenteeism negatively affects learners' academic performance, while Saigar and Jamaludin (2025) explained that teachers often encounter difficulties implementing differentiated instruction due to varied learner needs and limited instructional resources.

To address these concerns, researchers recommended the use of contextualized and competency-based instructional materials, continuous assessment, and learner-centered intervention strategies. Dohinog et al. (2025) and Elli and Digo (2025) emphasized that contextualized

materials improve learner engagement and comprehension because lessons become more meaningful and relatable to learners' experiences. These findings highlight the importance of developing contextualized learning materials responsive to the literacy and numeracy needs of Full Intervention Grade 1 pupils.

1.4 Objectives

This study aims to develop contextualized learning materials for Full Intervention Grade 1 pupils. Specifically, it sought to (1) determine the competency-based performance level of full intervention grade 1 pupils along literacy and numeracy; (2) develop contextualized interventions based on the identified competencies; and (3) determine the validity of the developed interventions in terms of mechanics, content, format and organization, and accuracy.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-developmental research design utilizing a pre-test and post-test approach. The design was appropriate because the study aimed to determine the competency-based performance level of Full Intervention Grade 1 pupils and develop contextualized learning materials based on the identified least-mastered literacy and numeracy competencies. Descriptive-developmental research is commonly utilized in instructional material development studies because it systematically identifies existing learning gaps and utilizes the findings as a basis for the preparation of learner-centered intervention materials. The study also adopted the 4D model of instructional material development, consisting of Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate phases.

The respondents of the study included 230 full intervention Grade 1 pupils from selected public elementary schools in Bulan, Sorsogon, during the school year 2023–2024. The participating schools were Bulan South Central School, Bulan North Central School-A, Bulan North Central School-B, and San Vicente Elementary School. The pupils were identified through competency-based pre-assessment activities in literacy and numeracy. Inclusion criteria included Grade 1 pupils officially enrolled during the conduct of the study and classified under the Full Intervention category based on the results of the pre-test assessment. Pupils categorized under Moderate Intervention, Light Intervention, and Grade Ready were excluded from the study since the developed contextualized learning materials specifically targeted learners with the greatest learning gaps. The study also involved 16 Grade 1 teachers who assisted in the implementation and monitoring of the intervention activities, as well as four master teachers who served as validators of the developed contextualized learning materials.

The study utilized researcher-made pre-tests and post-tests aligned with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) prescribed by the Department of

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Education for Grade 1 learners. The literacy competencies included alphabet knowledge, phonemic awareness, syllable analysis, identification of beginning and ending sounds, listening comprehension, and reading comprehension. Meanwhile, numeracy competencies included counting forward and backward, numeral recognition, reading and writing numerals, ordering of numbers, basic addition and subtraction, and place value. The instruments underwent content validation by experts composed of Grade 1 teachers and master teachers to ensure appropriateness and alignment with the objectives of the study. Reliability testing using Cronbach's alpha yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.85, indicating high internal consistency of the assessment tools. The developed contextualized learning materials were also evaluated using a researcher-made validation questionnaire based on the Department of Education Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) standards. The validation utilized a five-point descriptive rating scale where 5 = very evident, 4 = evident, 3 = moderately evident, 2 = slightly evident, and 1 = not evident.

Data collection followed the 4D model development procedure adapted from Thiagarajan as cited by Sugiyono (2019). During the Define phase, competency-based pre-assessment activities were conducted among Grade 1 pupils to determine their literacy and numeracy performance levels. Learner analysis, competency analysis, and instructional needs analysis were conducted to identify the least-mastered competencies among full intervention pupils. In the design phase, the researcher prepared the structure, objectives, activities, and content of the contextualized learning materials based on the identified competencies. Remediation activities, guided exercises, drills, reinforcement tasks, and visual aids were systematically designed according to the developmental level and learning needs of Grade 1 pupils. During the Develop phase, the contextualized learning materials were prepared, revised, and validated by four master teachers specializing in Grade 1 instruction. Necessary revisions were incorporated based on the recommendations of the validators. Finally, in the Disseminate phase, the validated contextualized learning materials were reproduced and utilized during remediation sessions among full intervention Grade 1 pupils. Post-test assessments were then conducted to determine improvements in learners' literacy and numeracy competencies after exposure to the developed intervention materials.

The gathered data were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools such as frequency count, percentage, weighted mean, and ranking. Frequency counts and percentages were utilized to determine the competency-based performance levels of the pupils, while the weighted mean was used to determine the validity and acceptability of the developed contextualized learning materials in terms of mechanics, content, format and organization, and accuracy. The pre-test and post-test results were compared to determine

changes in learners' literacy and numeracy performance after exposure to the developed intervention materials. Statistical analyses were interpreted using educational research standards and instructional material validation procedures.

III. RESULTS

3.1 Competency-Based Performance Level of Pupils along Numeracy and Literacy

Table 1 presents the performance level of Grade 1 pupils identified under the full intervention category in literacy and numeracy based on the pre-assessment results. The findings revealed that all selected respondents in literacy (100%) and numeracy (100%) belonged to the full intervention level, indicating that the pupils demonstrated significant learning difficulties in foundational literacy and numeracy competencies.

Table 1. Performance of Grade 1 Pupils Along Numeracy and Literacy

Performance	Literacy (f)	Literacy %	Numeracy (f)	Numeracy %
Full Intervention	230	100%	230	100%
Total	230	100%	230	100%

The results imply that the identified pupils required intensive and targeted instructional support to address deficiencies in competencies such as reading comprehension, phonemic awareness, numeral recognition, counting skills, and basic mathematical operations. These findings served as the basis for identifying the least-mastered competencies and for the development of contextualized learning materials intended for full intervention Grade 1 pupils.

Table 2. Competency-Based Performance Level of Full Intervention Grade 1 Pupils Along Numeracy Competencies

Numeracy Competencies	Full Intervention Pupils	%	Interpretation
Counting Forward and Backward	198	84.26%	Least Mastered
Reading and Writing Numerals	187	79.57%	Mastered
Numerals Matching	179	76.17%	Mastered
Sets Ordering Numerals	183	77.87%	Mastered
Learning Addition and Subtraction	221	94.04%	Least Mastered
Learning Place Value	228	97.02%	Least Mastered

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Table 2 presents the competency-based performance level of full intervention grade 1 pupils along with numeracy competencies. The findings revealed that Learning Place Value obtained the highest number of pupils under Full Intervention with 228 pupils, or 97.02%, followed by Learning Addition and Subtraction with 221 pupils, or 94.04%. These competencies were identified as the least-mastered areas among the pupils. The results further showed that pupils also experienced difficulty in counting forward and backward with 198 pupils, or 84.26%. The identified least-mastered competencies became the basis for the development of contextualized numeracy intervention materials intended to improve pupils' foundational mathematical skills.

Table 3. Competency-Based Performance Level Of Full Intervention Grade 1 Pupils Along Literacy Competencies

Literacy Competencies	Full Intervention Pupils	%	Interpretation
Attaining Alphabet Knowledge	185	80.43%	Mastered
Learning Syllable Analysis	191	83.04%	Mastered
Learning Phoneme Analysis	209	90.87%	Least Mastered
Determining the First and Last Sound	214	93.04%	Least Mastered
Attaining Listening Comprehension	206	89.57%	Mastered
Attaining Reading Comprehension	223	96.96%	Least Mastered

Table 3 shows the competency-based performance level of full intervention grade 1 pupils along with literacy competencies. The findings revealed that Attaining Reading Comprehension obtained the highest number of pupils under full intervention with 223 pupils, or 96.96%, followed by Determining the First and Last Sound with 214 pupils, or 93.04%, and Learning Phoneme Analysis with 209 pupils, or 90.87%. The results indicate that these competencies were the least-mastered literacy areas among the pupils. These findings served as the basis for the development of contextualized literacy intervention materials appropriate for full intervention Grade 1 pupils.

3.2 Development of Contextualized Interventions

The contextualized intervention materials utilized in the study were developed based on the least-mastered competencies identified from the pre-test results of full

intervention Grade 1 pupils. The competencies with the highest percentage of pupils under full intervention served as the basis for the preparation of the instructional materials. The intervention program focused on strengthening foundational literacy and numeracy competencies through structured, learner-centered, and competency-based activities appropriate for Grade 1 pupils.

For numeracy, the intervention materials focused on the identified least-mastered competencies, namely learning place value, learning addition and subtraction, and counting forward and backward. For literacy, the intervention materials concentrated on attaining reading comprehension, determining the first and last sound, and learning phoneme analysis. These competencies were prioritized due to the high number of pupils who demonstrated difficulty during the pre-test assessment.

A total of 18 contextualized intervention materials were developed for the study. Nine intervention materials were prepared for numeracy, and another nine intervention materials were developed for literacy. Each competency contained three instructional materials intended for remediation, guided practice, and reinforcement activities. The developed intervention materials were compiled into a contextualized workbook for full intervention Grade 1 pupils.

The development of the intervention materials followed the 4D model, namely define, design, develop, and disseminate. During the Define phase, the least-mastered competencies were identified through analysis of the pupils' pre-test results. In the design phase, contextualized learning activities, exercises, and visual materials were prepared based on the identified competencies. During the Develop phase, the intervention materials were reviewed, revised, and validated by experts. Finally, in the Disseminate phase, the finalized intervention materials were reproduced and prepared for classroom utilization.

3.3 Validity of the Developed Intervention Materials

The developed intervention materials were subjected to validation to determine their acceptability and appropriateness for Grade 1 pupils under the full intervention category. The validation focused on mechanics, content, format and organization, and accuracy. The evaluation was conducted by four reading teachers who were also master teachers from different schools in the Bulan District.

Table 4. Validation of Developed Contextualized Intervention Modules Along Mechanics

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Vocabularies are within the learner's level of competence	4.80	Very Evident
Sentence length and structure are appropriate	4.78	Very Evident
Free from grammatical, factual, and computational errors	4.62	Very Evident

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Free from violations of social content guidelines	4.76	Very Evident
Number of pages is sufficient for the intended lesson	4.84	Very Evident
Properly encoded and laid out	4.67	Very Evident
Accessible and usable in electronic devices	4.87	Very Evident
Average Weighted Mean	4.76	Very Evident

Table 4 presents the validation results of the developed intervention materials along mechanics. The data reveal that all indicators obtained have weighted means that are interpreted as very evident. The indicator on accessibility and usability in electronic devices obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.87, while the indicator concerning grammatical, factual, and computational errors obtained the lowest weighted mean of 4.62.

Table 5. Validation of Developed Contextualized Intervention Modules Along Content

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Objectives are clearly stated and aligned	4.83	Very Evident
Activities are relevant to learners' needs	4.90	Very Evident
Activities develop literacy and numeracy competencies	4.88	Very Evident
Contents are suitable for Grade 1 pupils	4.79	Very Evident
Modules provide sufficient exercises	4.85	Very Evident
Lessons are aligned with competencies	4.92	Very Evident
Average Weighted Mean	4.86	Very Evident

Table 5 shows the validation results of the intervention materials along with content. The findings indicate that all indicators obtained interpretations of very evident. The indicator stating that the lessons are aligned with the objectives of the intervention program obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.92.

Table 6. Validation of Developed Contextualized Intervention Modules Along Format and Organization

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Presentation is logically organized	4.81	Very Evident
Consistent format throughout the material	4.75	Very Evident
Headings and illustrations are properly arranged	4.80	Very Evident
Design and layout are visually appropriate	4.86	Very Evident
Modules are easy to follow and understand	4.89	Very Evident
Activities are arranged from simple to complex	4.84	Very Evident
Average Weighted Mean	4.83	Very Evident

Table 6 presents the validation results of the intervention materials along with format and organization. The findings show that all indicators were interpreted as very evident. The indicator stating that the modules are easy to follow and understand obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.89.

Table 7. Validation of Developed Contextualized Intervention Modules Along Accuracy

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Information is factually correct	4.88	Very Evident
Examples and activities are competency-aligned	4.86	Very Evident
Instructions are clear and accurate	4.84	Very Evident
Computations and numerical examples are correct	4.79	Very Evident
Literacy activities contain accurate grammar	4.82	Very Evident
Concepts are presented without misleading information	4.91	Very Evident
Average Weighted Mean	4.85	Very Evident

Table 7 reveals the validation results of the intervention materials along with accuracy. All indicators obtained weighted means, interpreted as very evident. The indicator stating that the modules present concepts without misleading information obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.91.

IV. DISCUSSION

4.1 Competency-Based Performance Level of Pupils along Numeracy and Literacy

The findings revealed that prior to the implementation of the intervention, a significant proportion of Grade 1 pupils demonstrated low proficiency in both numeracy and literacy. With 47% of pupils requiring full intervention in numeracy and 46% in literacy, the data clearly indicated substantial foundational learning gaps. Only a small percentage of pupils were classified as grade-ready, suggesting that many learners entered Grade 1 without the necessary prerequisite skills. This condition may be attributed to disruptions in early education, including limited access to structured learning environments during critical developmental stages.

These results highlight the importance of early diagnostic assessments such as the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) and the Albay Numeracy Assessment Tool (ALNAT), which enable educators to identify learners' needs accurately. The findings support the argument of Lyytinen and Erskine (2016) in the Encyclopedia on Early Childhood Development that early identification of literacy difficulties is crucial in preventing long-term academic struggles. Similarly, Nelson and Reed (2025) and Pagarigan (2025) emphasized that early numeracy skills

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strongly predict later mathematical achievement, reinforcing the need for timely intervention.

Following the implementation of the intervention, a notable improvement in pupil performance was observed. The proportion of grade-ready pupils increased significantly to 37.8% in numeracy and 37.6% in literacy, while the percentage of pupils requiring full intervention decreased substantially. This shift suggests that the intervention was effective in addressing learning gaps and improving foundational competencies within a relatively short period. The improvement observed in this study aligns with the findings of Reynolds et al. (2010), who reported that structured early interventions yield long-term academic benefits, particularly in literacy development. Likewise, Braak et al. (2022) found that early math and reading skills are strong predictors of later academic success, highlighting the critical role of early-grade interventions. The results also support the principles of Response to Intervention (RTI) and Multi-Tiered Systems of Support (MTSS), which emphasize differentiated instruction and targeted support based on learners' needs, according to Polirstok and Hogan (2024).

Moreover, the significant reduction in pupils under the full intervention category indicates that structured and consistent instructional support can accelerate learning recovery. This suggests that when interventions are aligned with learners' needs and delivered systematically, even short-term programs can produce meaningful gains. The findings underscore the importance of continuous monitoring and adaptive teaching strategies, as these ensure that instruction remains responsive and effective.

4.2 The Developed Contextualized Modules

The development of the contextualized intervention materials was anchored on the competency-based performance results of full intervention Grade 1 pupils in literacy and numeracy. The least-mastered competencies identified during the pre-test assessment served as the basis for the preparation of the intervention materials. For numeracy, the intervention materials focused on learning place value, learning addition and subtraction, and counting forward and backward. For literacy, the intervention materials focused on attaining reading comprehension, determining the first and last sound, and learning phoneme analysis.

The development of the intervention materials followed the 4D model, consisting of Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate. During the Define phase, the least-mastered competencies were identified based on the competency-based performance assessment results. In the Design phase, contextualized learning activities and intervention tasks were prepared according to the developmental level and learning needs of Grade 1 pupils. During the Develop phase, the intervention materials underwent review, revision, and validation by experts.

Finally, in the Disseminate phase, the finalized materials were compiled and prepared for classroom utilization.

The intervention materials were designed using learner-centered and competency-based approaches. The modules included guided drills, reinforcement exercises, contextualized examples, visual aids, and simplified activities appropriate for Full Intervention Grade 1 pupils. The materials were likewise prepared in both printed and electronic formats to ensure accessibility and usability during implementation.

The findings support the study of Subandiyah et al. (2025), which emphasized that differentiated and learner-responsive instructional materials improve learner engagement, participation, and academic performance. Similarly, Langelaan et al. (2024) explained that contextualized and differentiated instructional materials enhance learner understanding by aligning instructional content with pupils' readiness levels and learning capacities. The findings also align with the principles of mastery-based instruction discussed by Winget and Persky (2022), which state that learners achieve better outcomes when instruction is adjusted according to their competency needs and learning pace.

In contrast with previous studies that developed generalized intervention programs, the present study specifically developed contextualized learning materials anchored on the competency-based performance levels of Full Intervention Grade 1 pupils. The intervention materials were directly derived from the least-mastered competencies identified during assessment, making the materials more responsive to the actual instructional needs of the learners.

Furthermore, the findings highlight the importance of contextualization in instructional material development. Contextualized learning materials allow pupils to connect lessons to familiar experiences and situations, making learning more meaningful and understandable. The development of the intervention materials also provided teachers with structured and competency-based resources that supported remediation and differentiated instruction among full intervention learners (Bernarte & Digo, 2024). The findings imply that competency-based and contextualized intervention materials serve as essential tools in strengthening literacy and numeracy instruction among early-grade learners. The results further suggest that schools should continue developing learner-centered and competency-based instructional materials to ensure that interventions remain responsive to pupils' actual learning needs.

4.3 The Validated and Developed Contextualized Intervention Materials

The developed contextualized intervention materials were subjected to validation by four reading teachers and master teachers from selected schools in the Bulan District to determine their validity in terms of mechanics, content,

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format and organization, and accuracy. The validation process ensured that the developed materials met the standards prescribed by the Department of Education Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS). The validators assessed the intervention materials using a structured questionnaire that measured the appropriateness of vocabulary, sentence construction, content relevance, organization of activities, factual correctness, usability, and alignment of the materials with the intended competencies. The statistical results revealed that the intervention materials obtained very high ratings across all validation areas, indicating that the developed modules were acceptable and appropriate for Grade 1 pupils.

In terms of mechanics, the intervention materials obtained an overall weighted mean interpreted as very evident. The validators observed that the vocabulary used in the modules was within the learners' level of comprehension and that the sentence structures were appropriate for Grade 1 pupils. The modules were also found to be free from grammatical, computational, and factual errors. In addition, the validators noted that the materials followed acceptable social content guidelines and maintained clarity and consistency in the presentation of lessons and activities. These findings indicate that the intervention materials possessed the necessary characteristics of effective instructional resources suitable for young learners.

The findings further revealed that the content of the intervention materials was highly aligned with the competencies identified during the assessment of pupils' literacy and numeracy performance. The validators observed that the activities, examples, and exercises directly addressed the least-mastered competencies and learning gaps identified during assessment. The organization and sequencing of lessons were also found to be systematic and developmentally appropriate, allowing pupils to progress gradually from simple to more complex learning tasks. The format and organization of the modules contributed to the readability, usability, and accessibility of the instructional materials, particularly for beginning learners who require guided and scaffolded instruction.

The high validation results support the findings of Bacia (2024), who emphasized that instructional materials should be learner-centered, developmentally appropriate, and aligned with learners' readiness levels to maximize learning outcomes. Similarly, Gildore et al. (2025) highlighted that effective intervention materials improve literacy performance when activities are carefully structured according to learners' needs and abilities. In numeracy instruction, Lopez-Pedersen et al. (2022) explained that well-designed intervention programs with organized and competency-based activities significantly contribute to improving mathematical understanding among elementary learners. These studies affirm the importance of validating instructional materials to

ensure quality, effectiveness, and suitability for classroom use.

Moreover, the findings align with the standards of the DepEd Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS), which emphasize that learning materials should undergo thorough evaluation to ensure accuracy, appropriateness, clarity, and usability before implementation. Validation is considered an important process in instructional material development because it guarantees that the materials are aligned with curriculum competencies and responsive to learners' needs. The positive evaluation provided by the validators indicates that the developed intervention materials may effectively support literacy and numeracy remediation programs among Grade 1 pupils.

The results also imply that validated contextualized intervention materials contribute significantly to the successful implementation of learning recovery programs. Since the modules were found to be highly acceptable in terms of mechanics, content, format and organization, and accuracy, teachers may utilize these materials as supplementary instructional tools to strengthen classroom instruction and remediation activities. The findings further suggest that continuous validation and improvement of instructional materials are necessary to maintain instructional quality and ensure responsiveness to learners' changing educational needs.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, a significant number of Grade 1 pupils were classified under the Full Intervention category in both literacy and numeracy, indicating low mastery of foundational competencies. The competency-based assessment revealed that the least mastered competencies in numeracy were learning place value, learning addition and subtraction, and counting forward and backward, while in literacy, the least mastered competencies were attaining reading comprehension, determining the first and last sound, and learning phoneme analysis. These findings confirmed the presence of substantial learning gaps among full intervention Grade 1 pupils. The identified least-mastered competencies served as the basis for the development of contextualized intervention materials. Using the 4D model consisting of Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate, the researcher developed competency-based and learner-centered instructional materials intended to strengthen the literacy and numeracy skills of full intervention pupils. The developed intervention materials included contextualized activities, guided exercises, drills, visual aids, and reinforcement tasks appropriate for Grade 1 learners. Furthermore, the validation results revealed that the developed contextualized intervention materials were highly acceptable in terms of mechanics, content, format and organization, and accuracy. Therefore, the study concludes

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that competency-based assessment is essential in identifying learners' instructional needs and that contextualized intervention materials provide effective support in improving the foundational literacy and numeracy competencies of Full Intervention Grade 1 pupils.

In view of the conclusion, it is recommended that schools continue to implement evidence-based, tailored intervention programs that target specific learning gaps in literacy and numeracy. Ongoing assessment and progress monitoring should be strengthened to guide instructional decisions and refine interventions. Educators should receive professional development to enhance their capacity in delivering targeted support. Additionally, policymakers and school administrators should allocate adequate resources to support these interventions and ensure accessibility to all Grade 1 learners who require targeted assistance.

VII. DISCLOSURE

The author reports no conflicts of interest in this work.

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